

The Effects of Pandemics of COVID-19 on Domestic Violence

Cosmin Butură

*“Dimitrie Cantemir” Christian University - Faculty of Juridical and Administrative Sciences,
Bucharest, Romania, cosminbutura@yahoo.com*

ABSTRACT: Starting with the end of 2019, and so far, the pandemic challenged by the SARS-COV-2 virus called popular Corona Virus, has produced positive and negative effects from the perspective of different areas. If we are heading for the environment, we notice that statistics have shown a substantial increase in the ozone layer; The nature breathed and the air was cleaner, which was considered a positive effect. In the field of HORECA, hundreds of restaurants, cafes, bars, clubs and hotels closed, employers have to dismiss employees because of the long period of restrictions, so it is understood that the generated effect was negative. Also, in the social environment, education was under restrictions, pupils and students having to attend courses through online platforms, thus reducing inter-human socialization. However, not all the effects of the pandemic were visible to society and the press. During the emergency state, the population was blocked in housing, but this political action took into account the fact that every family is different in its own way? I therefore analyze the effects of the pandemy of COVID-19 among less perfect families from the perspective of forensics. Whether we accept or not, the idea of domestic violence is clearly described by annual statistics both at national and international level.

KEYWORDS: family, violence, forensics, indices, factors, pandemic, virus

Introduction

To begin with, I will analyze the notion of domestic violence. As a result, in the literature, it is defined as “threat or other violent behavior in families, which can be physical, sexual, psychological or economic and may include child abuses and violence in intimate partnership” (Usher, Bhullar, Durkin, Gyamfi, and Jackson 2020).

As we specified, during the COVID-19 pandemic, these negative factors have emerged on the social environment that, we can say, leaves physical and psychic fingerprints hard to eliminate. In the following, I will divide into two forms, the term violence in the family more precisely: the mild form and the aggravated form.

–*Easy form*, as it is called, refers to external factors that cause family participants in different acts likely to damage psychic integrity through injuries and here are words (insults), gestures or offensive acts.

The first easy factor that transforms the relationship between couples is the financial situation. As we know from statistics, many people have lost their jobs, some people entering technical unemployment and other people reaching debt failure. This is aspect is as dramatic as it can cause the person concerned to resort to inappropriate gestures, for example, a person who has just lost his job perceives this as a fear of social fall, therefore in the psychic. In depression, and depression is improved by alcohol or narcotic consumption.

In this category, as a rule, people exposed to the negative effects mentioned above are males. During this period, the lack of money and moral instability of men are treated differently, so every man will react according to nationality, religious cult, tradition, principles, etc. That is, in some cases, the man will go well for the hard time by consulting his life partner or other family members, while another man can react violently, considering that he is the foundation of the family and disappointed it, and and protect and maintain family.

We come to the conclusion that the stress caused leads to domestic violence in a mild form, for example, the life partner attempts to support it, but the active subject being too preoccupied with the resolution of the serious problem in his life, resorts to domestic violence,

being influenced by of toxic substances consumed (alcohol, drugs, etc.) Although we cannot consider this act, its obnoxiousness is characterized by the finality of the ignition and verbal injuries, both of which are alive (Bradbury-Jones & Isham 2020).

At international level, statistics show accelerated growth in emergency calls that have domestic violence in the forefront, and all due to the imposed isolation restrictions. For example, according to the statements of the Australian authorities, the crime rate decreased by 40% but the number of calls to the National Emergency Service increased by 5% on domestic violence. Another aspect at international level we are discovering in online search engines, thus according to Google statistics, the subject of domestic abuse was 75% (Commonwealth Bank Group 2020).

–*Aggravated form* refers to the acts of verbal violence that are temporary and turns into physical violence.

If at the first form, the victim is not physically damaged, that is not affected by body integrity, in this case, we have the opposite, as a result of the gravity of the shape is measured by means of an index. The index that determines the gravity of the form is the physical violence caused by one of the family members. An important aspect to be analyzed in the case of the two forms would be the relationship of social collaboration between the two. So, the aggravated form would also be caused by the involvement of the mild form. Deriving from this statement, we obtain the result that the aggravated form is divided into two independent and dependent forms, as follows:

–*Aggravated form independent*: It is the form of physical violence that does not require intervention from an external factor, as a result, violence starts from the trigger subject.

–*Dependent aggravated form*: It is the form of physical violence that depends on certain external factors that can turn into a plurality of new trigger topics in addition to the initial.

However, we understand that family violence is a sensitive, easy-triggered and controlled act according to the intensity of external factors and the main subject.

Isolation and domestic violence

Whether we like it or not, we must remind each other how the COVID-19 virus has spread, so I will show social effects on citizens, caused by political measures. Towards the end of 2019, the national alarm was given on a possible epidemic of Coronavirus and spreading through the air. Despite strict measures in order not to spread the virus and more, it reached early 2020 to cover a large infection surface in Europe, America and the rest of continents.

The measures imposed by the authorities were clear, decided to close administrative, social and private buildings thus isolating the socialization population. This isolation we look at it, families are isolated, so the life partners will have a high intensity of inter-human contact, they will further observe the defects of each, and the lack of family support in both camps will be strongly felt. Specifically, parents and relatives cannot physically socially intervene in the daily life of the couple. If the couple also has children, the situation is changing, because it isolates them in an unstable emotional, physical and financial family, produces negative effects on life (Campbell 2020).

The negative effects for the child are: social insulation, the desire to be violent, emotional instability, fear of parents, etc. But all of this will characterize the child, unfortunately, depending on his perception of things becoming shy or instigator.

A perfect storm

We have talked so far about family violence that can only occur in this pandemic in various factors and indices analyzed above. The question is, what is happening with families who have already had social and material instability before? For example, in the case of insulation measures, the conflict

between partners increases to the pandemic, and in the present case, the man consumes alcohol more regularly, maintaining it.

Let's analyze the partnership typology that already had problems in the family and we start with the partner who often consumes alcohol, in the present man. For example, before the pandemic, thanks to the applicant's job, the man fails to have too intense contact with his wife, but after approving the insulation measure at home, he has a contactinens, and blood alcohol intake increases exponentially. Because of this, his partner is no longer seen as a family member, as a friend, like a man of hope, etc. but on the contrary sees it as an enemy who penetrated his "land." So, isolation, which produces physical and psychological sedentarism, and alcohol consumption together makes a so-called wave of violence. Another important aspect to take into account is that during iozolation at home, victims can no longer request help so easily because the partners who hunt are continuously in the same dwelling. As a result, this isolation becomes a shield against the law for family abuses, beatings, offenses, humiliations, etc., keeping under anonymous (Davies & Batha 2020).

COVID-19 and coercive control

In order to discuss the notion of coercive control, we need to know what the general aspects of this are. As defined, the coercive element is "the element that holds power, control, which has the power to constrain".

In relation to the pandemic situation, the instigator partner is used by determining a coercive control mechanism more precisely it supplements the relationship with its partner during the isolation by fear, threat, sexual abuse, etc. If there is a possibility that because of the noise caused by family violence the neighbors to waters to the Single DeUrgency Service 112 to report the police caused by subjects. Officers can be presented at the suspect's door to get in touch with it and evaluate the domestic situation in the dwelling. This control of the police bodies does not prevent the aggressor from giving up and as a result of the pandemic situation and will not allow access to the dwelling, disinforming the acts committed against the life or concubine partner (Ruiu 2017).

I conclude by saying that, due to repeated abuses of aggressor, the victim induces a fear of demanding specialized medical treatment, more precisely refuses hospitalization.

Reimagination of support networks for people living in domestic violence in these difficult times

There is an international awareness of the population on the vulnerability of families and children. However, the company in which we live enters and in civic duties on the legal field and the security of the population and in the moral attributions to protect the person next to you. Thus, several non-governmental organizations or even governments itself have been asked for emergency departments in each state to pay interest in this period on domestic situations in housing.

Following these solutions, several NGOs and government departments have launched campaigns for informing and supporting victims who fall abuses during isolation. Many successful entrepreneurs have found different solutions to prevent family abuse, sponsored the governments and departments. Even once there is a civic sense for victims of suffering and we understand that the pandemic of COVID-19 is even difficult (Knowles 2020).

Conclusions

Within this article, we have generally treated tactical elements and forensic probation in the case of domestic violence, as if the complexity of the elements cannot fit the pages of the article.

As a result, we need to understand that the forensic field plays an important role in criminal investigations, with the activity of whichever focusing where any offense has been committed and analyzed each detail through numerous specific methods.

I believe that these acts made by active subjects are applied with a sense of responsibility during the periods in which the country of origin or whole globe goes through a disaster of proportions (huge explosions, natural disasters, biological wars, civil wars, etc.). They are used above mentioned as opportunities for applying bad plans. In these cases of crossroads, when political power is bound to resort to population isolation measures under the law, it greatly increases the rate of crime and family violence in this case. So, governments around the world must always have a well-designed social strategy to combat the possible abuse by one of the partners.

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